

Moderating role of moral disengagement in the relationship between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance: A proposed framework

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Abstract

Despite the fact that a considerable amount of research has contributed to our understanding of the underlying causes of workplace deviance, there is a paucity of research examining the role of organizational control in explaining deviant behavior at work. Furthermore, theory does not answer the research questions as to when and how perceived organizational control predict workplace deviance. To address this gap, this paper proposes a conceptual model linking perceived organizational control to workplace deviance, with moral disengagement as a potential moderating variable. It is expected that moral disengagement shall buffer the effect of perceived organizational control on deviance behaviour in workplace.

Keywords: Control theory, moral disengagement, organizational control, and workplace deviance

1. Introduction

Workplace deviance is an attitude, action, or behaviour of an individual or group of individuals that significantly violate organizational norms, traditions or ways of doing things and thereby threatening the effectiveness and or productivity of the organization, its members or both. This attitude of members has led to injuries, labour turnover and other negative effects on organization.

It is defined as a “voluntary behaviour that violates significant organizational norms and in so threatens the well-being of an organization, its members, or both” (Robinson & Bennett, 2015).

Workplace deviance is becoming increasingly important to researchers, practitioners and policy makers because it could have negative consequences on both organization and its members

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(Lawrence & Robinson, 2017; Spector & Fox, 2002). For example, in the United States (U.S), the use of drugs and alcohol in the workplace has been reported to have important negative consequences in increasing workplace injuries, turnover and absenteeism, as well as decreasing worker productivity, among others (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2022). Research also highlights that victims of interpersonal deviance (i.e., deviant behaviour directed at individuals) are more likely to experience job stress, low morale, decrease in productivity, as well as increase in fear and insecurity in the workplace (Henle, Giacalone, & Jurkiewicz, 2014).

Research further indicates that workplace deviance has indirect costs to organizations, in terms of reduced labour productivity (Bowling & Gruys, 2019; Johnson, 2009), lowered organizational commitment (Gardner & Johnson, 2001), higher rates of turnover (Namie, 2017), and damaged organizations' growth and profitability, among others (Lee & Ok, 2014). Work place deviance is largely studied according to whether such behavior is targeted against employing organization, its members, or both (e.g., Arthur, 2020; berry, ones, & Sackett, 2017; Hastings & O'Neill, 2009; Henle, Giacalone, Jurkiewicz 2014; Lim, 2002; Mulki, Jaramillo, & Locander, 2015; Salgado, 2002; Shamsudin, 2003).

A considerable amount of research has been undertaken to understand the underlying causes of workplace deviance. To date, some of the factors that have been studied in relation to workplace deviance include perceived organizational justice. (Aquino, Lewis, & Bradfield, 2019; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Ng, 2001; Near & Miceli, 2013; Shao, Rupp, Skarlicki, & Jones, 2013), perceived organizational support (Eder & Eisenberger, 2022; Ferris, Brown, & heller, 2009; O'Reilly & Chatman, 2010), and psychological contract breach (Bandura, 1977; Jensen, Opland,

& Ryan, 2019); Restubog, Bordia, & Tang, 2017; Zhao, Wayne, Glibkowski, & Bravo, 2017). Despite the abundance of research on workplace deviance, to date organizational researchers has offered no theoretical explanation as to when and how perceived organizational control relate to workplace deviance on the intervention of moral disengagement. Therefore, organizational control is concerned with formal organization where rules, regulations laws etc are documented and structured such that in the process the behaviour of people that form such organization are influenced to conform with laid down rules and regulations with the aim of achieving a set of objectives, while moral disengagement is concerned with cognitive recognition of the effect ones action against others such that the action will be less harmful to cause distress in discharging responsibilities. To this end, organizational control theory and moral disengagement theory may provide valuable insight for discussing and understanding the relationship between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance. Accordingly, this paper shall draw from these two theoretical perspectives to propose moral disengagement as a potential moderator between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance.

2 Literature Review and Proposition Development

2.1 Perceived Organizational Control and Workplace Deviance

While the workplace deviance construct has gained a lot of momentum for several decades now, literatures indicate a lack of agreement regarding not only the terminology used, but also the definition offered of what is considered to be a similar construct (Robinson & Benneth, 1997; Shamsudin, 2015). For example, researchers have given different names to the workplace deviance construct including, antisocial behavior (Giacalone & Greenberg, 1997), delinquency (Hogan &

Hogan, 1989), employee theft (Greenberg, 1990), workplace sabotage (Analoui, 2015; Harris & Ogbonna, 2015), workplace incivility (Andersson & Pearson, 2019), workplace aggression (Baron & Kenny, 1996), worker resistance (Thompson & Ackroyd, 2015), and cyberloafing (Lim, 2002). Although different terminologies are used, using different theoretical perspectives of organizational behavior, researchers seemingly agree that such behavior could bring harm to both individuals and organization (Shamsudin, Chauhan, & Kura, 2012).

On the other hand, organizational control refers to the “processes of influencing the behaviour of people as members of a formal organization with the goal of increasing the probability that they will achieve organizational goals” (Wilkes, Srinivasan, & Flamholtz, 2014). Prior research has established positive associations between perceived organizational control and various forms of workplace deviance. Specially, Kura, Shamsudin, and Chauhan (2012) showed that lack of organizational formal control increases the likelihood of employee deviant behaviour at work. Relatedly, disciplinary practices instituted by organizations have been found to be associated with decrease in cyberloafing (de Lara, Tacoronte, & Ding, 2015). From theoretical perspective, organizational control theory (Flamholtz, Das, & Tsui, 1999; Jaworski, 2020; Snell, 2012), postulates that formal control systems instituted by organizations play an important role in aligning the behavior of employees with the organizational goals. The aforementioned empirical and theoretical contributions, lead to the following proposition:

Proposition I: There will be a positive relationship between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance.

2.2 Moral Disengagement as a Potential Moderator

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Moral disengagement has been defined as “an individual’s propensity to evoke cognitions which restructure one’s actions to appear less harmful, minimize ones understanding of responsibility for one’s actions, or attenuate the perception of the distress one causes others” (Moore, 2022). Several scholars (Tenbrunsel & Smith-Crowe, 2022) have suggested that organizational researchers should attend to the role of cognitive process in explaining deviant behavior at work. Extent empirical studies have shown that moral disengagement relates to various forms of deviant behavior at work. For example, in line with the principle of moral disengagement theory, claybourn (2020) reported a significant positive relationship between moral disengagement and workplace harassment. The author further contended that “employees who reported relatively high tendencies for moral disengagement also were more likely to report having been subjected to more negative behaviours at work than those who reported low levels of moral disengagement (Claybourn, 2020). In a related study, Christian and Ellis (2014) have established a significant and positive relationship between dissatisfaction and deviant behavior at work among 429 support personnel in Malaysian public service organization.

Moral disengagement theory also postulates that employees who are morally disengaged have higher tendency to engage in behavior that harms an organization, its members, or both (Bandura, 2010; bandura, 2019; Robinson & Bennett, 2015). Drawing on organizational control theory and the theory of moral disengagement, we contended that laxity of organizational formal control increases workplace deviance by encouraging employees to morally disengage. We further argued that the strength of the positive relationship between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance is contingent upon moral disengagement because morally disengaged

individuals have a greater propensity to make decisions that advance organizational interests than their counterparts who are morally engaged (Moore, 2022). Therefore, based on the above empirical evidence and theoretical perspectives described previously, the following proposition is advanced;

Proposition II: Moral disengagement will moderate the relationship between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance.

2.3 Proposed Research Model

Building on the foregoing empirical evidence and theoretical perspectives, this paper proposes a conceptual model as illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Figure 1 helps to understand the potential moderating role of moral disengagement on the relationship between perceived organizational control and workplace deviance. Whereas

Perceived Organisational control (X) is Independent Variable

Workplace Deviance (Y) is dependent Variable

Moral Disengagement (M) is moderating Variable

Therefore, $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 M + U_t$

2.4 Conclusion

The preceding discussion has proposed perceived organizational control as an antecedent of workplace deviance, with moral disengagement as a potential moderator on this relationship. The next important stage is to carry out an empirical investigation towards validating the proposed framework illustrated in figure I. such empirical inquiry is particularly imperative given the significant cost of workplace deviance to both organizations and /or its members. Thus, by integrating organizational control theory and moral disengagement theory, one is able to see to what extent do moral disengagement buffer the effect of perceived organizational formal control on deviant behavior in the workplace.

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